

APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES
IN TRAINING FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION
TEACHERS

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Annotation: Physical education is and has always been an indispensable factor in the physical, moral, intellectual and spiritual development of the individual and an important means of promoting health. The process of reforming Uzbek national education involves the use of innovative technologies in physical education and sports. That is why there is an increase in attention to various kinds of innovations in the problems of physical education of students.

Key words: physical education, students, future teachers, innovative technologies.

Introduction. Innovation is a transformation based on new ideas and knowledge, and satisfies certain needs of an individual, society and the state. The main criteria for innovation are scientific novelty and its practical implementation [7, 8].

Innovative activity allows us to rethink the state of teaching activity and determine ways of its modernization. As D. Turdimurodov notes, innovation can be considered in two aspects: as a process and as a product (result) [2, 3, 6]. The innovative activity of a teacher can be considered as part of innovation in its various manifestations, namely: the development of innovative methods, organization, management, selection and implementation of original means.

The task of higher education teachers at the present stage is to choose such forms and methods of teaching that would allow the education applicant to show activity and creativity [1, 4, 5]. When choosing an innovative approach, the teacher must first of all work to create conditions for the development of the creative

potential of each student. Innovative learning develops the full potential of an individual's abilities and involves the development of the ability to interact with others in new atypical situations; it is based primarily on the pedagogy of cooperation, humane and personal technologies.

Its main principles are:

- finding a way out of problematic situations;
- inclusion of productive components in training - creativity;
- creating conditions for personal development (person-centered learning);
- innovation is a transformation, development of methods and results of people's activities.

The principles of humanistic philosophy, psychology, and pedagogy are embodied in personality-oriented technologies. This assumes the possibility of the emergence of a new social type of relationship between a teacher and applicants for education, the formation of relationships that are based on cooperation, mutual assistance, and co-creativity [7, 8, 9].

Innovative processes are implemented in such areas as: the formation of new educational content, the development and implementation of new pedagogical technologies. The development of innovative pedagogical technologies in physical education and sports at the present stage of educational development should be carried out in accordance with the criteria of manufacturability: scientific, systematic, guaranteed, manageable, mass [10, 11, 12]. Today, in the field of physical education and sports, there is already a certain set of innovative pedagogical technologies aimed at developing a healthy lifestyle among young people. Pedagogical technology is a set of psychological and pedagogical guidelines that determine the set and arrangement of forms, methods, techniques, teaching methods, and educational means.

Pedagogical technology is an organizational and methodological toolkit of the pedagogical process that allows you to structure teaching. Characterizing innovative

technologies of physical education, we can distinguish body-oriented, practice-oriented, personality-oriented, socially-oriented.

The purpose of using body-oriented technologies of physical education is to improve health, achieve normal physical development and general physical fitness of the younger generation in accordance with physical abilities. The goal of developing and introducing practice-oriented technologies into the process of physical education is to form motor skills using an organized system of pedagogical influences. The goal of developing and introducing personality-oriented technologies of physical education into the educational process is the formation of physical culture of the individual, the harmonious development of the physical and spiritual in a person, the formation of personality through the development of its physical potential [13, 14].

An innovative approach to education is aimed at a qualitative transformation of the educational process, the formation of innovative thinking, the development of skills in the skillful use of information and communication technologies, which will ensure the updating of didactics and methodology, the formation of a new, information-based way of life and professional activity. Innovative activities in the field of physical education should, first of all, be aimed at increasing physical activity and improving valeological literacy. To do this, it is necessary to create such technological models of health-improving physical culture that can have a positive impact on the attitude of young people towards their own health. The purpose of using information and communication technologies in education is to develop systems thinking among its applicants, promote the development of individual abilities, and help in consolidating new skills and abilities.

The use of information and communication technologies in physical education classes contributes to a more complete coverage of theoretical material, assimilation of information by education seekers and increasing their interest in developing a healthy lifestyle. In addition, information and communication technologies can be used to monitor the assimilation of educational material, diagnose health conditions,

and the level of physical fitness. Information and communication technologies become important in the process of explaining the technique of performing a new exercise or mastering a motor action, because it provides additional opportunities for demonstrating complex technical elements [15, 16].

Many educational technologies today are related to fitness, and the term “fitness” itself is quite common in scientific research and educational programs. Fitness is one of the modern methods of healing the body, which is aimed at improving a person’s health and physical fitness, developing flexibility, strength, endurance, and combating stress. Today there are a large number of fitness programs. Fitness classes help strengthen muscles and spine, improve posture. The training system is designed mainly in such a way as to train the body by gently influencing the muscles. It includes strength training, stretching exercises, and control over proper breathing.

The field of physical education and sports contains a significant number of methods that can satisfy a variety of human needs for physical activity and improvement of the body, both physical and psychological.

Conclusions. Along with traditional technologies, innovative ones are being actively introduced into educational programs in physical education and sports today. An important role belongs to the use of information and communication technologies to make learning more accessible and understandable. Fitness, by strengthening the muscle corset, improves posture and generally helps improve the health and psycho-emotional state of education seekers. In general, it should be noted that it is innovation that will make it possible to overcome the conservatism characteristic of education and will provide conditions for creating mechanisms for a flexible, prompt response to changes in the social order, the needs of the state, and the individual, which is considered as one of the most pressing tasks in the development of domestic education.

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